

Evaluation of Surgical Outcomes in Closed Bimalleolar Ankle Fractures: A Prospective Analysis of Union, Complications, and Functional Recovery**Raghuvver Meena¹, Girish Garg², Sandeep Kumar³, Mahaveer Meena⁴**¹3rd Year PG Resident, Department of Orthopaedic, JMC, Jhalawar²3rd Year PG Resident, Department of Orthopaedic, JMC, Jhalawar³3rd Year PG Resident, Department of Orthopaedic, JMC, Jhalawar⁴Professor, Department of Orthopaedic, JMC, Jhalawar

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Abstract:**Background:** Pott's fractures, particularly in the context of unstable ankle injuries, pose significant challenges in orthopedic practice. Surgical intervention, specifically open reduction, and internal fixation (ORIF) is often required to restore joint stability and function. This study evaluates the outcomes of surgical management in closed bimalleolar ankle fractures.**Methods:** This prospective study involved 30 patients with closed bimalleolar ankle fractures, managed surgically at SRG Hospital and Medical College, Jhalawar, from April 2022 to January 2024. Patients were assessed for postoperative complications, functional outcomes using the Olerud-Molander Ankle Score, and time to radiological union.**Results:** The majority of patients (83.33%) experienced no postoperative complications. Functional outcomes were favourable, with 40.00% of patients achieving an excellent score and 33.33% achieving a good score. Radiological union was observed in 73.33% of patients within 8-10 weeks, indicating a rapid recovery associated with surgical intervention.**Conclusion:** ORIF is an effective approach for managing closed bimalleolar ankle fractures, offering excellent functional recovery, minimal complications, and a swift return to mobility. Surgical intervention should be prioritized in cases of unstable ankle fractures to optimize patient outcomes.**Keywords:** Pott's fractures, ankle injuries, open reduction internal fixation (ORIF), surgical outcomes, functional recovery, radiological union.

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Introduction

Ankle injuries, particularly Pott's fractures, are among the most common weight-bearing orthopedic traumas encountered in clinical practice. The ankle joint, known for its high congruity, plays a crucial role in maintaining stability and enabling locomotion. Disruptions in the joint's normal articular relationship can lead to significant biomechanical dysfunction and progressive arthrosis, underscoring the importance of effective management strategies. [1,2]

The clinical management of ankle fractures hinges on determining the stability of the fracture. Stable fractures may be successfully treated conservatively; however, unstable fractures often require surgical intervention for optimal outcomes. Open reduction and internal fixation (ORIF) have been widely recognized as superior to conservative treatments for managing unstable ankle fractures, as they allow for precise anatomical reduction and stabilization of the joint. [3]

The complexity of ankle fractures lies in their involvement of both bony and ligamentous components, making accurate diagnosis and treatment challenging. Advanced imaging techniques, such as Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), have revolutionized the ability to diagnose ligamentous injuries alongside bony fractures, enabling a comprehensive approach to treatment. This detailed visualization is crucial for developing tailored interventions that address the multifaceted nature of ankle injuries, ultimately restoring joint stability and function.[4]

Despite advancements in surgical techniques, the management of ankle fractures remains an area of ongoing research and refinement. Traditional treatment methods, such as cast immobilization, have been associated with complications like joint stiffness, persistent pain, and swelling. These limitations have led to a growing consensus in favor of surgical fixation techniques, particularly for Pott's fractures, to restore anatomical alignment,

facilitate early mobilization, and improve long-term outcomes.[5]

This shift towards surgical management reflects a broader trend in orthopedic care that prioritizes the restoration of function and the prevention of long-term disability. Research continues to explore the most effective surgical techniques and postoperative rehabilitation strategies to ensure that patients achieve optimal recovery. The use of scoring systems, such as the Olerud-Molander Ankle Score, provides a structured approach to evaluating patient outcomes, offering valuable insights into the effectiveness of treatment strategies. [6,7]

Overall, the management of Pott's fractures demands a meticulous approach that combines advanced diagnostic techniques, precise surgical intervention, and comprehensive postoperative care. This approach is essential for achieving favourable outcomes and enabling patients to return to their daily activities with minimal long-term impairment.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Setting: This prospective study was conducted at SRG Hospital and Medical College, Jhalawar, from April 2022 to January 2024. It focused on the surgical management of Pott's fractures, with a minimum follow-up period of 6 months. A total of 30 cases were included in the study after receiving approval from the institutional ethics committee.

Radiological Assessment: All patients meeting the inclusion criteria underwent radiological evaluation, including antero-posterior, lateral, and Harris mortise view X-rays of the ankle joint.

Inclusion Criteria

- Age range: 21 to 60 years.
- Patients with closed Pott's fractures.
- Patients fit for surgery and who provided informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria

- Age below 21 years or above 60 years.
- Associated fractures around the ankle joint.
- Injuries older than three weeks.
- Open injuries with dislocation.
- Skin diseases affecting the ankle region.
- Previous arthrodesis at the target site.
- Metabolic bone disorders or pathological fractures.
- Underlying neuromuscular disorders.
- Patients unfit for surgery.
- Lack of patient consent.

Preoperative Evaluation

Upon arrival, patients were assessed using the ABCDE approach. Resuscitative measures, including IV fluids and oxygen therapy, were administered as needed. Temporary posterior plaster splints were applied, and the affected limb was elevated. Comprehensive histories were collected, and diagnostic imaging (AP, lateral, and mortise views) and routine blood tests were performed to ensure appropriate preoperative planning.

Surgical Intervention: Surgery was performed under spinal, epidural, or general anesthesia. The surgical procedure involved:

• Medial Malleolus

Open Reduction and Internal Fixation (ORIF) using an antero-medial approach. The fracture was reduced and stabilized with a 4mm cannulated cancellous screw or tension band wiring.

• Lateral Malleolus

Fixation was achieved using a lateral approach with a 1/3rd tubular plate, fibular locking plate, K-wire/Rush nail, or a 4mm cannulated cancellous screw.

- After fixation Syndesmotic injury was checked intraoperatively if ankle unstable syndesmotic screw was also used.

Following fixation, wounds were closed in layers and dressed in sterile compression bandages. A below-knee posterior slab was applied to maintain the limb in a neutral position.

Postoperative Care and Follow-Up:

Postoperative care included IV antibiotics for 3 days, followed by oral antibiotics for 5 days. Analgesics were administered as needed, and the limb was kept elevated in a BK posterior splint. Active toe and knee movements were encouraged from the first postoperative day. Sutures were removed after two weeks, and a below-knee slab was reapplied for four weeks. Ankle and toe exercises were initiated in a compression bandage. Patients were followed up every 4 weeks, with syndesmotic screws removed at 8 to 12 weeks as radiological signs of union were observed. The Olerud-Molander Ankle Score was used to evaluate patient outcomes during follow-ups.

Results

The study included 30 patients who underwent surgical management for Pott's fractures, with a focus on assessing postoperative complications, functional outcomes, and time taken for radiological union.

Case Illustrations

Outcomes Based on Subjective Scoring

The functional outcomes were evaluated using the Olerud-Molander Ankle Score, which classifies results into four categories: excellent, good, fair, and poor. As detailed in Table 2, 40.00% of patients (n=12) achieved an "Excellent" outcome with scores above 90, while 33.33% (n=10) were classified as "Good" with scores between 81-90. A smaller percentage of patients, 16.66% (n=5), fell into the "Fair" category with scores between 60-80, and 10.00% (n=3) had "Poor" outcomes with scores below 60.

Time Taken for Radiological Union

The time required for radiological union varied among the patients, as summarized in Table 3. The majority, 73.33% (n=22), achieved radiological union within 8-10 weeks post-surgery. A further 16.66% (n=5) reached union between 10-12 weeks, while 6.66% (n=2) and 3.33% (n=1) showed union at 12-15 weeks and more than 15 weeks, respectively.

Table 1: Complications post-surgery

Complication Type	No. of Patients	Percentage (%)
Deep Infection	1	3.33
Superficial Infection without Skin Necrosis	1	3.33
Arthritis	1	3.33
Implant Failure	1	3.33
Non-Union	1	3.33
Nil (No Complications)	25	83.33
Total	30	100.00

Table 2: Functional Outcomes Based On Subjective Scoring

Outcome Category	Score Range	No. of Patients	Percentage (%)
Excellent	>90	12	40.00
Good	81-90	10	33.33
Fair	60-80	5	16.66
Poor	<60	3	10.00
Total	-	30	100.00

Table 3: Time Taken for Radiological Union

Time (Weeks)	No. of Patients	Percentage (%)
8-10	22	73.33
10-12	5	16.66
12-15	2	6.66
>15	1	3.33
Total	30	100.00

Complications post-surgery

As shown in Table 1, the majority of patients (83.33%) experienced no postoperative complications. However, complications were observed in a small subset of patients, with 3.33% of patients each experiencing deep infection, superficial infection without skin necrosis, arthritis, implant failure, and non-union.

Discussion

The findings from this study on the surgical management of closed bimalleolar Pott's fractures provide valuable insights into the outcomes associated with open reduction and internal fixation (ORIF). The results underscore the efficacy of surgical intervention in achieving favorable outcomes, particularly in terms of functional recovery and radiological union, while highlighting the relatively low incidence of postoperative complications.[8]

The majority of patients (83.33%) in this study experienced no postoperative complications, which is a promising outcome that supports the use of ORIF in managing unstable ankle fractures. The low incidence of complications, including deep infection, superficial infection without skin necrosis, arthritis, implant failure, and non-union (each observed in only 3.33% of patients), aligns with existing literature that advocates for surgical intervention in such cases. These findings are consistent with studies that emphasize the importance of precise anatomical reduction and stabilization to minimize the risk of postoperative complications and ensure better functional outcomes. [9,10]

The functional outcomes, assessed using the Olerud-Molander Ankle Score, revealed that a significant proportion of patients (40.00%) achieved an excellent score, indicating that ORIF effectively restores ankle function in most cases. The fact that 33.33% of patients had good outcomes further supports the effectiveness of the surgical approach. However, it is noteworthy that 16.66% of patients had only fair outcomes, and 10.00% had poor outcomes, suggesting that while ORIF is generally successful, certain factors may influence the variability in recovery. These factors could include the severity of the initial injury, patient comorbidities,

and adherence to postoperative rehabilitation protocols. [11,12]

The time taken for radiological union, with 73.33% of patients achieving union within 8-10 weeks, is indicative of the rapid recovery associated with surgical management of Pott's fractures. This finding is significant as it highlights the advantage of surgical intervention in reducing the duration of immobilization and facilitating earlier return to weight-bearing activities. The shorter recovery time compared to conservative management methods, such as cast immobilization, is an important consideration for both patients and clinicians, especially in cases where a quick return to function is desired.[13]

The study's limitations include its relatively small sample size and the single-center design, which may limit the generalizability of the findings. Future research with larger, multi-center trials could provide more robust data to confirm these results and further explore factors affecting the variability in outcomes. Additionally, long-term follow-up studies are needed to assess the sustainability of the functional outcomes observed in this study and to monitor for potential late complications such as post-traumatic arthritis.[14]

Conclusion

The surgical management of closed bimalleolar Pott's fractures via ORIF has proven to be effective in achieving excellent functional outcomes, minimizing complications, and facilitating timely radiological union. This approach should be considered a preferred treatment modality for unstable ankle fractures, ensuring optimal recovery and the restoration of joint function.

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